

OcMOD - Observations closer to MOdel Data

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Abstract

The preparation of observational data from public authorities for research purposes in climate modelling often involves individual, repetitive efforts across research groups. This pilot project aims to establish general guidelines for processing observational datasets from public authorities to facilitate research accessibility, standardisation, and adherence to FAIR principles. In collaboration with the German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ) and the German Weather Service (DWD), and with input from the scientific community, we processed and published the COSMO-REA6 regional reanalysis dataset for improved usability by researchers. This workflow has been distilled into a blueprint to guide similar endeavours in climate science and related disciplines.

¹ Based on the CRediT Contributor Roles Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

I. Introduction

In the realm of Earth system research, the availability and accessibility of high-quality data are crucial for advancing scientific understanding and driving meaningful insights. This is particularly evident in the context of climate modelling, where the utilisation of climate model data plays a pivotal role in a wide range of research endeavours, climate impact analyses, and climate change adaptation strategies. To ensure that the model data chosen is suitable for the individual research question or application, this data is usually validated against reference data from observations. Commonly, model data and observational data are obtained from different sources - model data from the file servers of high performance computers (HPCs) such as the HPC Levante of the German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ) and observational data from public authorities, such as the German Meteorological Service DWD. Despite a trend towards more open data policies during the last decade (partly due to directives as eg. GeoIDG², the PSI directive³ or INSPIRE⁴), the findability and accessibility to Governmental datasets can be far from what is considered optimal within the so called FAIR guidelines (*Wilkinson et al., 2016*), which give recommendations towards the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reuse of scientific data. Also the latter two pillars of the FAIR principles may not be optimally followed. This is due to the usage of different (meta)data standards and data formats in the climate model research community and by the public authority. A broad range of users (*e.g. climate modellers, impact modellers, climate scientists, providers for climate services and education*) are dealing with these efforts, sometimes with one and the same dataset (Fig. 1). Recognizing the significance and potential of government collected data for research, the pilot project OcMOD ("Observations Closer to MOdel Data"), funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure for Earth System Research (NFDI4Earth) focuses on bridging the gap between reference data provided by public authorities and the output from climate models to enable seamless analysis and evaluation for the researchers. This shall be achieved by exemplarily elaborating guidelines on how to make data from Governmental agencies available to diverse research communities - in a way that is in accordance with the FAIR principles.

In a collaboration between the DKRZ and the DWD, and with the support and feedback of the scientific community, notably the two BMBF-funded projects ClimXtreme^{1,2,5} and RegiKlim^{3,6}, who act as stakeholders, the high-resolution regional reanalysis COSMO-REA6 (Bollmeyer et al., 2015) shall be processed as the mentioned example. ClimXtreme is focusing on the investigation of climate extremes in the past and future and within

² Geologiedatengesetz - <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/geoldg/> (in German)

³ Public Sector Information Directive - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32013L0037>

⁴ Directive regarding an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32010R1089>

⁵ <https://www.fona.de/de/massnahmen/foerdermassnahmen/climxtreme.php> (in German) and <https://climxtreme.net>

⁶ <https://www.fona.de/de/massnahmen/foerdermassnahmen/regionale-informationen-zum-klimahandeln.php> (in German) and <https://www.regiklim.de> (in German)

Fig. 1: Adaptation of important datasets of public authorities for research purposes is an effort often repeated by several research groups for one and the same dataset.

RegIKlim, high resolution climate model simulations will be carried out in close collaboration with certain focus regions, to implement adaptation strategies. Both projects use the evaluation framework FREVA⁷ (Kadow et al., 2021) adapted for individual project needs, to evaluate and analyse climate model results and observational data. This framework is also successfully used in education e.g. at Freie Universität Berlin (FUB). All model and observational data have to be available in CMOR-standard (CMOR: Climate Model Output Rewriter⁸), which is used for the big climate Coupled Model Intercomparison Projects (CMIP, with its latest phase, CMIP6⁹) as well as CORDEX (COordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment¹⁰). These datasets are provided via the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF¹¹) and represent an important contribution of climate information for the regularly composed Assessment Reports of the Intergovernmental Panel of Climate Change (IPCC¹²). Via the DKRZ infrastructure, FREVA comes with direct access to the data provided by the DKRZ administered ESGF node. For the two stakeholder projects, COSMO-REA6 is an essential dataset to be standardised and available within the FREVA framework. The reanalysis dataset has been intensively used in other applications too, e.g. related to the energy sector (Kaspar et al., 2020), but it has not yet been integrated into research infrastructures of the Earth System Research community. This makes it an ideal candidate for the OcMOD pilot, to elaborate a template for the incorporation of governmental data products into global research data distribution infrastructures following the FAIR guidelines, thereby enhancing the usability of data for various research applications and ensuring enduring data access as well as citability and traceability through the assignment of unique Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs¹³). Thus, this effort contributes to realising the FAIR principles, fostering

⁷ www.xces.dkrz.de

⁸ <https://cmor.llnl.gov/>

⁹ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phase-6-cmip6/>

¹⁰ <https://cordex.org/>

¹¹ <https://esgf.llnl.gov/>, or the DKRZ node: <https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/projects/esgf-dkrz/>

¹² <https://www.ipcc.ch/>

¹³ <https://datacite.org/create-dois/>

collaboration and maximising the potential impact of governmental data products within the global research data distribution infrastructure.

Results

There are four main outcomes of this pilot project:

- 1) The result of a survey to determine the requirements of potential users of the standardised COSMO-REA6 data set: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11108657>
- 2) A workflow to standardise the selected COSMO-REA6 parameters according to a CORDEX/CMIP like data and metadata standard in the form of a gitlab repository that holds scripts, configuration and controlled vocabulary (CV):
<https://gitlab.dkrz.de/dicad-pp/ocmod>
- 3) The COSMO-REA6 dataset, thoroughly quality controlled and standardised using said workflow, and published via the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) as well as the long term archive World Data Centre for Climate (WDCC). For the latter data repository, the dataset was attributed a DataCite DOI: https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/CR6_EU6
- 4) A description that serves as a blueprint, containing a condensed and generalised version of the standardisation workflow, as well as all other planning and processing steps, in written and visualised form. These documents shall serve as guidelines for efforts that aim at making public authority data sets available for research purposes:
 - Detailed description (german): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16418207>
(eingereicht, im Review)
 - Schema (english): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948875>
 - Schema (german): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15878879>

a) Implemented Solution

DKRZ and DWD, in collaboration with the climate research community, established the framework for processing and providing the COSMO-REA6 dataset in a research-friendly format. This process aligned with FAIR guidelines and addressed specific requirements from projects like ClimXtreme^{1,2} and RegIKlim³.

Key Requirements and Standards

Community Tool Compatibility: Ensured compatibility with existing domain-specific standards (CMIP, CORDEX) built upon Climate Forecast (CF) Conventions¹⁴.

Data Standard: Developed in consultation with project stakeholders, consisting of:

Data Reference Syntax (DRS): Defines a standardised naming convention for files and directories, including structure and metadata.

Controlled Vocabulary (CV): A controlled term set aligned with DRS rules, describing scientific parameters, and coordinate information formats.

¹⁴ <http://cfconventions.org/>

File Format: Employs netCDF4¹⁵, a self-describing, array-oriented scientific data format supporting compression.

Technical Considerations

The focus was on providing data in a format adhering to established standards and maximising compatibility with existing research tools and practices.

The selection of scientific parameters of the COSMO-REA6 dataset that should be processed has been determined by evaluating a community survey that has been conducted for that purpose, while considering constraints stemming from limited resources, such as disk space and manpower. These parameters consequently had to be mapped to their counterparts in the data standard. Besides a potentially necessary aggregation (eg. temporal averaging or vertical interpolation), the mapping information includes in part complex variable diagnostics, unit conversions, processing comments and positive flux directions, owing to the fact that not always simple direct mappings are possible. Eventually, the data processing and standardisation were performed with tools and toolkits of the (climate) research community as well as the public authority. Their application was orchestrated by a run script and followed by a quality control (QC) that performed several checks on the data (eg. for consistency across files and statistical outliers) and also verified compliance with the data standard. The applied tools and toolkits were:

- **CDOs (Climate Data Operators)**¹⁶: toolkit for the processing of climate data in multiple formats. It includes many operators covering simple and complex operations. Examples are vertical interpolation, horizontal remapping, arithmetic and statistical operations. In this project the CDOs were used for the aggregation and diagnostic operations on the data. Moreover, the “cdo cmor” operator was used, providing an user-friendly interface to the CMOR library.
- **FIELDXTRA**¹⁷: toolbox for the manipulation of numerical weather prediction (NWP) model or gridded observational data. Being an official post processing tool of the Consortium for Small Scale Modelling (COSMO Consortium), it was used for the vertical interpolation from the COSMO model native hybrid height levels to pressure levels and for de-staggering (i.e. horizontal interpolation from model grid cell vertices to cell centres for vector data).
- **CMOR** (and “cdo cmor”¹⁸): library to rewrite gridded climate model or observational data to be compliant with a specified data standard. In this project the CDO operator “cmor” was used, which facilitates the application of the CMOR library and connects it to the CDO data read and write capabilities.
- **Standardisation WebGUI**¹⁹: web based graphical user interface originally developed for the standardisation of CMIP6 data. Allows to create mapping information databases. The

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5065/D6H70CW6>

¹⁶ <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/COSMO-ORG>

¹⁸ https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/wiki/CDO_CMOR_Operator

¹⁹ <https://c6dreq.dkrz.de>

content of the database can be downloaded in the form of tables or processing scripts that execute the diagnostics and standardisation by applying CDO operators.

- **NCOs (netCDF Operators)**²⁰: toolkit for the processing of climate data in netCDF and related formats, offering similar operations as the CDOs. In this project, the capabilities of the “ncap2” and “ncatted” operators were used to perform manipulations of the coordinates and metadata that “cdo cmor” did not support.
- **QA-DKRZ**²¹: Beside a custom quality checker also the established tool QA-DKRZ was used. It was developed at DKRZ to verify compliance of netCDF files with data standards such as CORDEX, CMIP5/6 and the CF conventions. Additionally, it is able to perform checks on the data itself, like a check for consistency in coordinates and metadata across files and for statistical outliers.

The standardised COSMO-REA6 data is available on disk for users of the DKRZ HPC Levante. Furthermore the data has been published on one of the DKRZ administered ESGF nodes with each file and the parameter datasets having been assigned a Persistent Identifier (PID). The PIDs allow a referencing of the data after possible changes to the data location or transfer of ownership. The DKRZ makes use of PIDs based on the handle system. Their PID service is incorporated in the framework of the European ePIC consortium²².

The long-term availability and reusability of the data is secured by a long-term archival in the DKRZ long-term archive WDCC (World data Centre for Climate). Besides the storage of the data in a tape archive, this is connected with the attribution of a DOI including citation information. Hereby the DKRZ makes use of the DataCite data publication service. The assignment of a DOI warrants long-term access to the data, with the data and metadata remaining unchanged.

The data publication is followed by the data curation: users of the data are supported, faulty data or metadata corrected (errata) as well as PIDs and (meta)data maintained.

This pilot project has been presented in the following articles, posters and talks:

- NFDI4Earth Pilot Proposal:
<https://nfdi4earth.de/images/22KasparObservationsclosertoModelDataOcMOD.pdf>
- NFDI4Earth Pilot Kickoff - Presentation - not publicly available
- NFDI4Earth Pilot Midterm Meeting - presentation:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7360809>
- NFDI Community Workshop Standardisierung - presentation - not publicly available
- Hannover Open Science Community Meeting 2023 - poster - not publicly available
- NFDI4Earth Planary 2023 - poster - not publicly available
- Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI) 2023 - abstract and poster - not publicly available

²⁰ <https://nco.sourceforge.net/>

²¹ <https://qa-dkrz.readthedocs.io/en/latest/introduction.html>

²² <http://www.pidconsortium.net/>

b) Data and Software availability

The corrected, standardised and published data can be freely accessed via

- ESGF - <https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/projects/cosmo-rea/>
- WDCC (long term archive) - https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/CR6_EU6

The DWD provides the dataset in its raw / original format:

- DWD opendata: https://opendata.dwd.de/climate_environment/REA/COSMO_REA6/

The standardisation scripts and the collected metadata are available via the following gitlab repository:

- <https://gitlab.dkrz.de/dicad-pp/ocmod>

The published standardised data as well as the data processing and standardisation scripts fall under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)²³. However, the licences of the tools and toolkits the scripts apply may differ from that. For example, the scientific use of the FIELDEXTRA tool of the COSMO Consortium has been granted in a bilateral licence contract with DWD (as a partner of the COSMO Consortium).

c) Innovation and FAIRness

One of the aims of this pilot project was to enhance the FAIRness of the COSMO-REA6 dataset and thereby increase the usability of the dataset by the climate research community. The following measures have been undertaken to be in accordance with the four FAIR guidelines:

- Findability

In consultation with the DWD, persistent identifiers were assigned to the standardised datasets published via the ESGF. Additionally, a digital object identifier (DataCite DOI) incl. citation information was assigned and linked to the previously created PIDs when this data was long-term archived. Suitable project, experiment and source descriptions as well as representative tags and references have been assigned to the published datasets, ensuring findability via the data repositories' web portals and web search engines.

- Accessibility

ESGF is an established global data repository with web interface and API for data search, access and download. The data has been published on the DKRZ administered data node. In the short and mid term, the data is available on disk for seamless data analysis by DKRZ users or for real time download.

For long term accessibility, the data has been archived in the World Data Centre for Climate. Therefore, when the demand for instantaneous downloads and access on disk decreases so much that it no longer needs to be provided in that way, the data will still be available for a delayed download via the WDCC web portal, for which

²³ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

the data will be automatically retrieved from tape to the WDCC cache. In a similar way the ESGF data portal will then link to the long term archived data files. Data access via ESGF and WDCC is unrestricted.

- **Interoperability**

The COSMO-REA6 regional reanalysis data was converted to be in accordance with domain-specific and widely-used data and metadata standards (based on the standards of CORDEX, CMIP, which are often generally referred to as “CMOR standards”, with CMOR being the library or tool rewriting the data in the specified format). After the standardisation, the data and the compliance with the standard were thoroughly quality controlled. Analysis and post processing tools of the climate research community (eg. ESMValTool, NCO, CDO, xarray, etc.) support or request this standard, ensuring the required interoperability of the data product.

- **Reusability**

The data is obtainable and usable under the CC By 4.0 licence. Furthermore, through the adoption of domain-specific (meta)data standards, documentation of provenance, provided citation information (as part of the DOI), and a data curation of the published long-term archived data by DKRZ data management experts supported by DWD climate scientists, the reusability of the data is warranted.

Challenges and Gaps

All planned results of this pilot project could be achieved. With the experience of both involved institutes, stemming for example from collaborations within projects like CMIP6 and ClimXtreme, challenges could be overcome before evolving into true obstacles. Notable challenges are thereafter described.

This project involves different tasks, which require waiting times: the consultation of the scientific community for feedback, eg. via surveys, the collection of the necessary metadata and compilation of processing relevant information regarding the transformation or diagnostic of scientific parameters of the dataset, the agreement of licence and citation information, etc. Therefore the duration of the pilot was extended from the usual twelve to eighteen months, while keeping overall working hours and funds dedicated to this project fixed. This then allowed the time intensive feedback loops between the DWD as provider of the original data, the DKRZ as processor and publisher of the standardised data as well as the research community (interested research groups and stakeholders) to take place.

In that regard, it is essential that all partners in such a project are aware that it is required to continuously invest time and work to compile the processing information and metadata needed to standardise and publish the data. The success depends on the initiative and willingness of all involved partners to contribute their expertise to the desired outcome, which in case of this project was given.

Moreover, a close collaboration with the potential users of the final data product is fundamental for a satisfying data product. Hence, an initial community survey was conducted by DWD and DKRZ to obtain the requirements of the interested research groups in terms of the scientific parameters, the vertical grid(s) the data is provided on as well as general feedback and wishes for similar projects in the future. For the same purpose a continuous feedback loop was kept up with the stakeholders of the project.

One of the requests of the interested researchers consisted in the provision of the 3D variables not only on the native vertical model grid (hybrid height), which the commonly used CDO toolkit does not support, but on pressure levels. To achieve this, the FIELDEXTRA toolbox of the COSMO Consortium had to be applied. Due to its native compatibility with the COSMO model output it is perfectly suited for this purpose. However, a bilateral licence contract had to be set up between the DKRZ and the DWD (representing the COSMO Consortium). This and the installation of and familiarisation with the tool took time, but eventually the desired results could be produced.

Lastly, owing to the GeoNutzV ordinance²⁴, that regulates the provision of German federal geodata, the data would have to be provided freely, with the requirement to give credit to the creator of the data. The DWD as the producer of the COSMO-REA6 dataset, the DWD agreed to apply the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0), which is an internationally comprehensible licence that is known and accepted in research.

²⁴ <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/geonutzv/> (in German)

Relevance for the Community, NFDI4Earth and Future Directions

A comprehensive community survey conducted among potentially interested research groups served to glean valuable insights regarding the demand and utility of a regional reanalysis dataset like COSMO-REA6 for the European domain. Together with a long-term data curation, including persistent identifier maintenance, publication of corrected data files, and potential errata information, ongoing usability is guaranteed.

This community-driven approach not only validated the planned efforts but also provided critical feedback for future refinements. Implementing the feedback, a new version of COSMO-REA6 (“R6G2”) includes:

- **Expanded Output Parameters:** Addressing previously unmet user requirements, the new version incorporates additional output parameters.
- **Enhanced Spatial and Temporal Resolution:** Data will be provided on more atmospheric height and pressure levels, leveraging finer grid resolution and a longer timeframe (1979 - present) offered by the state-of-the-art ERA5 reanalysis from ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) that is used to force the reanalysis.
- **Improved Model Version:** The new realisation employs a newer version of the COSMO model²⁵.
- **Standardisation Workflow Application:** The developed standardisation workflow, potentially with adjustments and extensions to accommodate the modified output, is planned for application to the new version.

This pilot project is strengthened by the active participation of leading stakeholders from two nationally funded projects, ClimXtreme and RegIKlim, both focussing on climate change assessment, research and climate adaptation strategies. However, the standardised COSMO-REA6 data extends its reach to a broader audience. This includes impact modellers, climate researchers and educational institutions, who benefit from relevant data readily accessible through ESGF. By making data from public authorities highly standardised and easily accessible, the project significantly increases data visibility, potentially leading to wider dissemination and utilisation.

To amplify the reach and impact of the newly published standardised COSMO-REA6 dataset, news articles were disseminated through various channels. This included publications on the DKRZ and DWD websites, targeted distribution via relevant mailing lists, and personalised communication via email with research groups who contributed feedback and participated in the initial survey.

Without the support of NFDI4Earth, it would have been difficult to realise this project, which brings together representatives from the research sector and public authorities.

Furthermore the dataset was already used for research purposes. The data was at the centre of

²⁵ https://www.cosmo-model.org/content/model/cosmo/releaseNotes/cosmo_5.04d.htm

DataXplorers, a cross-community hackathon of the NFDIs NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Earth and NFDI4Microbiota, where participants used the richness of the data for creative solutions. For this purpose, selected datasets were converted to the zarr format and uploaded to DKRZ swift cloud²⁶. The success of this endeavour highlights the value of linking governmental datasets to research needs and sets the stage for future collaborations.

This means that Measure 2.5 Advancing Tools and Measure 2.3 Governmental Data as well as the participants of the NFDI4Earth Academy have also benefited directly from the project and the data itself.

The assembled blueprint offers guidance for similar ventures of making the data of public authorities available for the research community and the set up scripts provide the further ability to integrate more and more reanalyses or observational datasets into ESGF, and also supporting the efficient education of students in climate research. The availability of more datasets encourages applications of server-side analysis as well as the development of new tools, integrating model output the same as observations.

²⁶ Access to the COSMO-REA6 data stored in the cloud is demonstrated in a Jupyter Notebook available in the project GitLab repository (<https://gitlab.dkrz.de/dicad-pp/ocmod/>).

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